

Naphthoisocoumarins and Related Compounds

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Several naphthoisocoumarins have been prepared. They have been converted into the related isochromens, isocarbostyrils and isobenzopyrylium salts.

FEW isocoumarins condensed at 3,4 positions are known¹⁻⁵. It was desirable to explore this area and the present communication deals on experiments on the synthesis of naphtho (1' 2' : 3,4) isocoumarins and their transformation products. For this a practical synthesis of the α -(*o*-carboxyphenyl)- γ -phenyl-butyric acid (Va) appeared desirable. Although attempts to effect a stobbe condensation of phenylacetaldehyde with diethyl homophthalate led to the self-condensation of the former but the corresponding condensation of phenylglyoxal with homophthalimide was effective yielding phenacylidene homophthalimide (Ia). This compound exhibited a strong tendency to dimerise to a high melting compound m.p. 295°-96° (M⁺ 554) which may be formulated provisionally (IV) Bailey *et al.* Reduction of (Ia) either catalytically or by sodium dithionite followed by hydrolysis gave the keto acid (IIIa) along with a considerable amount of benzoic acid. The formation of benzoic acid is surprising and in the case of corresponding 3,4-dimethoxy derivative veratric acid was the sole isolable product of hydrolysis. This hydrolytic step has put limitations on the present route. The acid (IIIa) on reduction (Clemmensen) to (Va) and thence cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid afforded dihydronaphthoisocoumarin (IXa). On dehydrogenation (IXa) naphthoisocoumarin (Xa) in quantitative yield.

The inadequacy of the present route mentioned above forced us to adopt the route employed by Bailey *et al.*⁷. Thus the condensation of phthalaldehydic acid with acetophenone in presence of alkali afforded the phthalide (VIa) which on treatment with KCN and hot hydrochloric acid gave the pyrroloisocoumarin (VIIIa) which was smoothly hydrolysed by alkali to give the keto-acid (IIIa). Subsequently, the keto-acids (IIIb), (IIIc), (IIId) and (IIIe) were prepared and the first two reduced, cyclised and dehydrogenated to the corresponding coumarin (Xb) and (Xc).

The dihydronaphthoisocoumarins (IXa), (IXb) and (IXc) on treatment with alcoholic ammonia passed on to isocarbostyrils (XIa), (XIb) and (XIc) which

were dehydrogenated to the naphthoisocarbostyrils (XIIa), (XIIb) and (XIIc).

The dihydronaphthoisocoumarin (IXa) on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride and on subsequent cyclisation by acid gave the isochromen (XIII).

Unlike ordinary isochromens, the dihydronaphthoisochromen is fairly stable. The isochromen (XIII) was catalytically reduced to tetrahydronaphthoisochromen. The related *gem* dialkyl and diarylisochromens were easily prepared. Thus, dihydronaphthoisocoumarin (IXa) afforded *gem*-dimethyldihydronaphthoisochromen (XIV, R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H) with excess of methylmagnesium iodide. Similarly, the compounds (XIV, R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃, R₃ = H), (XIV, R = CH₃, R₁ = R₃ = H, R₂ = OCH₃) and (XIV, R = Ph, R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H) were prepared. Dihydronaphthoisocoumarin (IXa) on treatment with one mole of phenylmagnesium bromide gave the corresponding carbinol which on treatment with 60% perchloric acid afforded the isobenzopyrylium salt (XV, R = Ph). Two other isobenzopyrylium salts (XV, R = C₆H₄OCH₃-*p*) and (XV, R = C₆H₄CH₃-*p*) were similarly prepared. These crystalline red salts are quite stable.

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. The i.r. spectra were determined in KBr disc and u.v. spectra in ethanol (95%).

4-Phenacylidenehomophthalimide (Ia) :

To a cold solution of homophthalimide (5 g) in pyridine (75 ml), a solution of phenylglyoxal hydrate (10 g) in pyridine (25 ml) was added and the mixture left at room temperature for 2 hrs. The mixture was poured into water giving 4-phenacylidenehomophthalimide which crystallised from acetic acid in pink needles (6 g; 72.5%) m.p. 225° (lit.⁶, m.p. 225°). (Found : C, 73.4; H, 3.7; N, 5.1. Calc. for C₁₇H₁₁O₃N: C, 73.6; H, 4.0; N, 5.0%); ν_{max} 1675 cm⁻¹ (keto carbonyl) and 1708 cm⁻¹ (cyclic imide carbonyl).

4-Phenacylhomophthalimide (IIa) :

(i) A suspension of 4-phenacylidenehomophthalimide (3 g) in ethylene glycol monomethyl ether (60 ml),

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a, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$

c, $R_1 = R_3 = H, R_2 = OCH_3$

b, $R_1 = R_2 = OCH_3, R_3 = H$

d, $R_1 = OCH_3, R_2 = R_3 = H$

e, $R_1 = R_2 = H, R_3 = OCH_3$

containing palladised charcoal (0.5 g; 10%) was hydrogenated at room temperature under normal pressure. When the absorption of hydrogen ceased the mixture was boiled and filtered. On cooling 4-phenacylhomophthalimide separated as colourless prisms, m.p. 248° (lit⁶, m.p. $248^\circ-50^\circ$) (Found :

C, 72.8; H, 4.4; N, 4.0. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{13}O_3N$: C, 73.1, H, 4.7; N 5.0%), ν_{max} 1680 cm^{-1} and 1710 cm^{-1}

(ii) To a solution of 4-phenacylidenhomophthalimide (1 g) in boiling dioxan (20 ml) a solution of sodium hydrosulphite (1 g) in water (5 ml) was added,

XIII

XIV

XV

when a solid separated. On working up (IIa) was obtained as colourless plates, m.p. 247° (Found : C, 73.0; H, 4.5; N, 5.0%).

β -Benzoyl- α -o-carboxyphenylpropionic Acid (IIIa) :

A solution of 4-phenacylhomophthalimide (2 g) in (N) pot. hydroxide (40 ml) was refluxed for 6 hrs. in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The cooled solution was acidified when a gum separated which was dissolved in (N) pot. hydroxide, the alkaline solution carefully acidified till a brown precipitate separated which was removed and the filtrate made strongly acidic when a gum separated which on crystallisation (acetic acid) afforded yellow needles (0.3; 14%), m.p. 180° - 81° (decomp.) (lit.⁶, m.p. 180° - 81°). (Found : C, 68.3; H, 4.4. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$: C, 68.4; H, 4.7%); ν_{max} 1708 cm^{-1} (acid carbonyl) and 1690 cm^{-1} (keto carbonyl). The aqueous layer, after separation from the gum, yielded benzoic acid, m.p. 121° .

4-(3',4'-Dimethoxyphenacylidene) homophthalimide (Ib) :

3,4-Dimethoxyphenylglyoxal (5 g), pyridine (2 ml) and benzene (100 ml) were taken in flask fitted with a soxhlet containing homophthalimide (2.5 g). The flask was heated on a water bath for 12 hrs., the separated solid crystallised in needles (0.8; 8%) from dioxane, m.p. 253° (Found : C, 67.3; H, 4.5; N, 4.2. $C_{19}H_{15}O_5N$ requires C, 67.6; H, 4.5; N, 4.1%); ν_{max} 1708 cm^{-1} and 1685 cm^{-1} .

4-(3',4'-Dimethoxyphenacyl) homophthalimide (IIb) :

A suspension of (Ib) (1 g) in ethyl alcohol (75 ml) containing 10% palladised charcoal (50 mg) was hydrogenated. The product (IIb) crystallised as prisms (0.2 g; 19%) from ethyl acetate, m.p. 170° (Found : C, 67.1; H, 5.0; N, 4.0. $C_{19}H_{17}O_5N$ requires C, 67.2; H, 5.0; N, 4.1%); ν_{max} 1710 cm^{-1} and 1690 cm^{-1} . This phenacylphthalimide (0.5 g) in (N) potassium hydroxide (10 ml) was refluxed for 6 hrs. and gave veratric acid, m.p. 181° .

α -(o-Carboxyphenyl)- γ -phenylbutyric Acid (Va) :

A suspension of (IIIa) (3 g) in a mixture of water (15 ml), conc. hydrochloric acid (25 ml) and toluene (25 ml) containing amalgamated zinc (6 g) was refluxed for 30 hrs. On working up the product was esterified with diazomethane to give the related ester (b.p., 190° - $200^{\circ}/0.6\text{ mm}$). (Found : C, 73.1;

H, 6.6. $C_{16}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 73.0; H, 6.4%); ν_{max} ; 1725 cm^{-1} and 1735 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl). This ester on hydrolysis gave (Va) as colourless needles, m.p. 141° . (Found : C, 71.5; H, 5.4. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.6%).

3',4'-Dihydronaphtho(1',2':3,4) isocoumarin (IXa) :

A mixture of α (o-carboxyphenyl)- γ -phenylbutyric acid (1 g) and polyphosphoric acid (5 g) was heated over water bath for 16 hrs. The dihydronaphthoisocoumarin (IXa) separated in cream coloured needles (0.4 g; 45.5%) from acetic acid, m.p. 167° . (Found : C, 82.1; H, 5.0. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 82.2; H, 4.8%); ν_{max} 1710 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl); λ_{max} 228 nm (log ϵ , 3.71), 310 nm (log ϵ , 3.53), 323 nm (log ϵ , 3.57).

Naphtho(1',2' : 3,4) isocoumarin (Xa) :

A solution of 3',4'-dihydronaphtho(1',2':3,4) isocoumarin (1 g) in *p*-cymene (2 ml) containing 10% palladised charcoal (50 ml) was refluxed for 10 hrs. at 185° . The product crystallised from *p*-cymene in needles, m.p. 191° . (Found : C, 82.7; H, 4.0. $C_{17}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 82.9; H, 4.1%); ν_{max} 1740 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl); λ_{max} 266 nm (log ϵ , 4.02), 291 nm (log ϵ , 3.32).

3',4'-Dihydronaphtho(1',2' : 3,4) isochromen (XIII) :

A suspension of 3',4'-dihydronaphtho(1',2' : 3,4) isocoumarin (0.1 g) in ether (50 ml) was treated with an excess of lithium aluminium hydride (0.1 g) and stirred for 4 hrs at 0° . The isochromen (XIII) distilled at 204° - $10^{\circ}/0.9\text{ mm}$ to give a solid (60 mg; 64%), m.p. 81° - 82° . (Found : C, 87.2; H, 6.3. $C_{17}H_{14}O$ requires C, 87.1; H, 6.0%); ν_{max} 1620 cm^{-1} (double bond).

1',2',3',4'-Tetrahydronaphtho(1',2' : 3,4) isochroman :

A solution of the above isochromen (0.1 g) in ethyl acetate (10 ml) containing 10% palladised charcoal (20 mg) was hydrogenated to give isochroman which crystallised from methanol in colourless plates, (50 mg; 49.6%) m.p. 94° - 95° . (Found : C, 86.3; H, 6.4. $C_{17}H_{16}O$ requires C, 86.4; H, 6.8%); λ_{max} 213 nm (log ϵ , 3.32) and 270 nm (log ϵ , 3.33).

(1,1-Diphenyl-3',4'-dihydronaphtho(1',2' : 3,4) isochroman (XIV, R = C_6H_5 R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H) :

A solution of (IXa) (0.24 g) in benzene (15 ml) was added to solution of phenylmagnesium bromide,

derived from magnesium (80 mg) and bromobenzene (0.48 g) in ether (20 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 4 hrs. when the solution assumed a dark colour. The solution was decomposed with acid and the product on chromatography was obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 174°. (Found: C, 91.0; H, 7.6. $C_{29}H_{22}O$ requires C, 90.1; H, 5.7%).

1,1-Dimethyl-3',4'-dihydronaphtho (1',2' : 3,4) isochromen (XIV, R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H) :

This was similarly prepared with an excess of methylmagnesium iodide and obtained as an oil, b.p. 190°-195°/0.9 mm. (Found: C, 87.0; H, 6.5. $C_{19}H_{18}O$ requires, C, 87.0; H, 6.9%); ν_{max} 1380 cm⁻¹ and 1360 cm⁻¹ (gem dimethyl). This on dehydrogenation gave the corresponding naphthoisochromen, m.p. 85°. (Found: C, 87.5; H, 6.0. $C_{19}H_{16}O$ requires C, 87.6; H, 6.1%).

1,1-Dimethyl-3',4'-dihydro-6',7'-dimethoxynaphtho(1',2' : 3,4) isochromen (XIV, R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃, R₃ = H) :

A solution of dihydronaphthoiso coumarin (IXb) (0.1 g) in benzene (8 ml) was treated with excess of methylmagnesium iodide, derived from magnesium (50 mg) and methyl iodide (2 ml) and the product (50 mg; 38%) crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 105°. (Found: C, 78.2; H, 6.7. $C_{21}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 78.2; H, 6.9%); ν_{max} 1372 cm⁻¹ and 1350 cm⁻¹ (gem dimethyl).

1,1-Dimethyl-3',4'-dihydro-6'-methoxynaphtho (1',2' : 3,4)-isochromen (XIV, R = CH₃, R₁ = R₃ = H, R₂ = OCH₃) :

The isochromen was similarly prepared from (IXc) and distilled at 200°-205°/0.9 mm as a colourless oil (Found: C, 82.1; H, 6.8. $C_{20}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 82.1; H, 6.9%); ν_{max} 1378 cm⁻¹ and 1352 cm⁻¹ (gem dimethyl).

1-Phenyl-3',4'-dihydronaphtho(1',2' : 3,4) isobenzopyrylium Perchlorate (XV, R = Ph) :

Phenylmagnesium bromide, derived from magnesium (40 mg) and bromobenzene (0.21 g) was added to a solution of (IXa) (0.36 g) in benzene (5 ml) when a jelly separated. The complex was decomposed after 4 hrs. with ammonium chloride (10 ml; 20%); the resulting oil from ether solution was treated with perchloric acid (0.5 ml) in acetic anhydride (1 ml) with stirring and when dry ether (5 ml) was added to the reddish solution. The isobenzopyrylium salt was obtained as bright red leaflets (0.27; 46.5%) when crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 263° (decomp.) (Found: C, 67.5; H, 4.0. $C_{28}H_{17}O_5Cl$ requires C, 67.7; H, 4.1%).

1-p-Tolyl-3',4'-dihydro (1',2' : 3,4) isobenzopyrylium Perchlorate (XV, R = C₆H₄-CH₃(o)) :

This was similarly prepared using *p*-tolylmagnesium bromide and crystallised from acetic acid in shining red leaflets, m.p. 241° (decomp.) (Found: C, 68.1; H, 4.3. $C_{24}H_{19}O_5Cl$ requires C, 68.2; H, 4.5%).

1-*p*-Anisyl-3',4'-dihydro (1',2' : 3,4) isobenzopyrylium Perchlorate (XV, R = C₆H₄-OCH₃(*p*)) :

Prepared as above using *p*-anisylmagnesium bromide, the salt crystallised from acetic acid in bright red leaflets, m.p. 278° (decomp.) (Found: C, 66.1; H 4.8. $C_{24}H_{19}O_5Cl$ requires C, 65.7; H, 5.0%).

3,4-Dimethoxyphenacylphthalide (VIb) :

Acetoveratrone (5 g) was mixed with warm alcohol (36 ml) containing phthalaldehydic acid (5.8 g), potassium hydroxide (3 g) in water (5 ml) was added to the mixture drop by drop. On working up the phthalide (6 g; 69%) crystallised from 50% acetic acid as colourless prisms, m.p. 158°-60° (Found: C, 69.0; H, 5.2. $C_{18}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 69.2; H, 5.1%); ν_{max} 1760 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl) and 1665 cm⁻¹ (keto carbonyl). The properties and analysis of other phenacylphthalides are recorded in Table 1.

5'-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl) pyrrolo (2',3' : 3,4) isocoumarin (VIIIb) :

The above phthalide (5 g) dissolved in boiling ethylene glycol monomethyl ether (20 ml) containing crystalline sodium acetate (2.5 g) was heated at 100°, and potassium cyanide (3 g) in water (6 ml) added drop wise during 3 mins. After 10 min. the solution was cooled, acidified when nitrile separated as an oil, which solidified. Its melting point could not be recorded as the substance passed into the corresponding 5'-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-pyrrolo (2',3' : 3,4) isocoumarin spontaneously above 121°. ν_{max} 2256 cm⁻¹ (nitrile), 1715 cm⁻¹ (acid carbonyl) and 1670 cm⁻¹ (keto carbonyl).

To the solution of above cyano compound (3 g) in acetic acid (20 ml), hydrochloric acid (6 ml; 17%) was added and heated for few minutes when a yellow precipitate immediately separated. The compound crystallised from pyridine in needles (2.5 g; 88.7%), m.p. 289°-90°. (Found: C, 70.8; H, 4.4. $C_{19}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 71.0; H 4.7%); ν_{max} 1722 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl). The properties and analysis of other 5'-phenylpyrrolo(2',3' : 3,4) isocoumarins are recorded in Table 2.

α -(2-Carboxyphenyl)- β -(3,4-dimethoxybenzoyl) propionic Acid (IIIb) :

5-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl) pyrrolo(2' 3' : 3,4) isocoumarin (5 g) was refluxed with 10% sodium hydroxide (50 ml) for 4 hrs. The solution was filtered and acidified when the acid (3 g; 54%) separated crystallising from acetic acid in clusters of needles, m.p. 186°-87°. (Found: C, 63.3; H, 5.0. $C_{19}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 63.7; H 5.0%). ν_{max} 1705 cm⁻¹ (acid carbonyl) and 1665 cm⁻¹ (keto carbonyl). The properties and analysis of other α -(2-carboxyphenyl)- β -benzoylpropionic acids are recorded in Table 3.

α -(2-Carboxyphenyl)- γ -(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl) butyric acid (Vb) :

The keto acid (IIIb) was reduced by Clemmensen method as before and isolated as its ester (b.p.

TABLE 1—PHENACYLPHthalIDES (VI)

Compound	M.P.	Cryst. shape	Formula	Found	Calc.	$\nu_{max}(cm^{-1})$
1. ($R_1 = R_3 = H, R_2 = OCH_3$)	115–17°	Colourless prisms	$C_{17}H_{14}O_4$	C : 72.3 H : 4.9	72.3 5.0	1762 1675
2. ($R_1 = OCH_3, R_2 = R_3 = H$)	124–25°	Shining white needles	$C_{17}H_{14}O_4$	C : 72.2 H : 4.8	72.3 5.0	1762 1680
3. ($R_1 = R_2 = H, R_3 = OCH_3$)	134°	Colourless needles	$C_{17}H_{14}O_4$	C : 72.2 H : 4.9	72.3 5.0	1765 1668

TABLE 2—5'-PHENYLPYRROLO(2',3' : 3,4)ISOCOUMARIN (VIII)

Compound	M.P.	Cryst. shape	Formula	Found	Calc.
1. $R_1 = R_3 = H, R_2 = OCH_3$	249°	Yellow bars	$C_{18}H_{13}O_3N$	C : 74.2 H : 4.4	74.2 4.5
2. $R_1 = OCH_3, R_2 = R_3 = H$	265–66°	Yellow needles	$C_{18}H_{13}O_3N$	C : 74.0 H : 4.4 N : 4.6	74.2 4.5 4.8
3. $R_1 = R_2 = H, R_3 = OCH_3$	209°	Yellow needles	$C_{18}H_{13}O_3N$	C : 73.9 H : 4.3 N : 4.6	74.2 4.5 4.8

 TABLE 3—2-(2-CARBOXYPHENYL)- β -BENZOYLPROPIONIC ACIDS (III)

Compounds	M.P.	Cryst. shape	Formula	Found	Calc.	ν_{max}
1. $R_1 = R_3 = H, R_2 = OCH_3$	188°	Colourless needles	$C_{18}H_{16}O_6$	C : 65.7 H : 4.8	65.9 4.9	1720, 1680
2. $R_1 = OCH_3, R_2 = R_3 = H$	177°	Colourless needles	$C_{18}H_{16}O_6$	C : 65.8 H : 4.8	65.8 4.9	1710, 1685
3. $R_1 = R_2 = H, R_3 = OCH_3$	(decomp) 169° (decomp)	Colourless prisms	$C_{18}H_{16}O_6$	C : 65.8 H : 4.8	65.8 4.9	1705, 1665

 TABLE 4—2-(2-CARBOXYPHENYL)- γ -PHENYL BUTYRIC ACIDS (V)

Compound	M.P.	Cryst. shape	Formula	Found	Calc.
1. $R_1 = R_3 = H, R_2 = OCH_3$	did not solidify	—	—	—	—
2. $R_1 = OCH_3, R_2 = R_3 = H$	140°	Colourless needles	$C_{18}H_{18}O_5$	C : 68.7 H : 5.6	68.8 5.8
3. $R_1 = R_2 = H, R_3 = OCH_3$	137°	Colourless needles	$C_{18}H_{18}O_5$	C : 68.6 H : 5.6	68.8 5.8

220°–25°/0.9 mm) (Found : C, 67.6; H, 6.3. $C_{21}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 67.7; H, 6.5%).

The ester on hydrolysis gave the acid (Vb) as a gum. The properties and analysis of other acids are given in Table 4.

3',4'-Dihydro-6',7'-dimethoxynaphtho(1',2' : 3,4) isocoumarin (IXb) :

The above acid (Vb) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid as before giving the naphthoisocoumarin (IXb) which crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 173°. (Found : C, 73.8; H, 5.1. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 74.0; H, 5.2%); ν_{max} 1718 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} 235 nm (log ϵ , 3.53) and 335 nm (log ϵ , 3.28). Similarly the isocoumarin (IXc) crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish needles, m.p. 168° (ν_{max} 1718 cm^{-1}) (Found : C, 77.5; H, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3$ requires, C, 77.7; H, 5.0%).

6',7'-Dimethoxynaphtho(1',2' : 3,4) isocoumarin (Xb) :

The isocoumarin (IXb) (0.1 g) was refluxed with *p*-cymene (3 ml) containing 10% palladised charcoal

(20 ml) at 180° for 10 hrs. Then it was worked up in the same way as described for the preparation of (Xa) when the isocoumarin (Xb) (30 mg; 30%) was obtained in prisms, m.p. 213° (Found : C, 74.4; H, 4.3. $C_{19}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 74.4; H, 4.6%); ν_{max} 1740 cm^{-1} .

6'-Methoxynaphtho (1',2' : 3,4) isocoumarin (Xc) :

This was similarly prepared and obtained as colourless needles (20 mg; 20%), m.p. 182°–83° from *p*-cymene. (Found : C, 78.0; H, 4.2. $C_{18}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 78.2; H, 4.4%); ν_{max} 1721 cm^{-1} .

Dihydronaphthoisocarbostyryl (XIa) :

This was prepared by heating the isocoumarin (IXa) with ethanolic ammonia, crystallised from acetic acid in prisms, m.p. 266° (Found : C, 82.5; H, 5.4; N, 5.8. $C_{17}H_{13}ON$ requires C, 82.6; H, 5.2; N, 5.7%); ν_{max} 1658 cm^{-1} (carbonyl). This on dehydrogenation gave naphtho (1',2' : 3,4) isocarbostyryl (XIa), m.p. 325° (lit.⁸, m.p. 329°); ν_{max} 1650 cm^{-1} .

3',4'-Dihydro-6',7'-dimethoxynaphtho(1',2' : 3,4) isocarbostyryl (XIb) :

The dihydronaphthoisocoumarin (Xb) was converted into the isocarbostyryl (80 mg), m.p. 293°-94° (Found : C, 74.0; H, 5.2; N, 4.4. $C_{19}H_{17}O_3N$ requires C, 47.2; H, 5.6; N, 4.5%); ν_{max} 1642 cm^{-1} . This dihydro isocarbostyryl (XIb) was dehydrogenated to give the isocarbostyryl (XIb), m.p. 324° (Found : C, 74.7; H, 4.9; N, 4.6%); ν_{max} 1658 cm^{-1} (carbonyl).

3',4'-Dihydro-6'-methoxynaphtho(1',2' : 3,4) isocarbostyryl (XIc) :

The isocoumarin (IXc) was similarly converted into the isocarbostyryl; m.p. 242°-43° (Found : C, 77.9; H, 4.5; N, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 77.9; H, 4.4; N, 5.0%); ν_{max} 1640 cm^{-1} . This dihydronaphthoisocarbostyryl on dehydrogenation in *p*-cymene gave 6'-Methoxynaphtho (1',2' : 3,4) isocarbostril (XIIc) as colourless plates, m.p. 309° (Found : C,

78.2; H, 4.6; N, 4.9. $C_{18}H_{13}O_2N$ requires C, 78.5; H, 4.7; N, 5.1%); ν_{max} 1655 cm^{-1} (carbonyl).

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